

Statement by the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (IICD), 6 August 2001

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STATEMENT BY THE
INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING
(IICD)
6 August 2001

To: The Rt Hon. John Reid, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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"In a recent meeting with the Commission, the IRA representative proposed a method for putting IRA arms completely and verifiably beyond use.

"We are satisfied that this proposal meets the Commission's remit in accordance with the Governments' scheme and regulations.

"Based on our discussions with the IRA representative, we believe that this proposal initiates a process that will put IRA arms completely and verifiably beyond use."

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 6 August 2001

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CAIN contains information and source material on the conflict and politics in Northern Ireland.
CAIN is based within Ulster University.